

Dumitru SUCIU, *Evoluția ideii de Europă unită*, București, Edit. Historia, 2007, 346 p.

Reeditarea în formă științifică a unui mai vechi eseu al autorului (2002), lucrarea *Evoluția ideii de Europă unită* încearcă să ofere cititorului un model de înțelegere a premiselor ce au condus, începând cu sfârșitul perioadei moderne, la cristalizarea actualei formule politice europene. Structura sa tripartită deosebește, oarecum, acest volum de clasicele abordări ale temei, în special prin aceea că Dumitru Suciuc insistă, pe mai bine de o treime din numărul de pagini, asupra evenimentelor anilor 1918-1919, pe care le consideră esențiale pentru evoluția ulterioară a continentului.

Primul capitol este dedicat în întregime acestei perioade, accentul căzând pe rolul Marilor Puteri occidentale, și în special al diplomației americane, în reconstrucția politică a zonei central-est europene și impunerea tinerelor democrații în locul „*ihiozaurilor*” și a „*dinozaurilor din vechile ere geologice*”. Un al doilea capitol are ca obiect prezentarea multitudinii de planuri de unificare europeană propuse în secolul al XIX-lea și în perioada interbelică. Această „preistorie” a construcției europene se caracterizează, conform autorului, prin două trăsături distincte: „*permanența ideii de Europă Unită, provenită din cele mai elevate și mai luminate minți și faptul că aproape întotdeauna ea s-a manifestat împotriva violenței, a tiraniei de orice fel, împotriva războaielor, pentru democrație internă și internațională și egalitate între națiunile ce urmau să se asocieze în această comunitate politică.*” (p. 226). Al treilea și ultimul capitol urmărește etapa postbelică a construcției europene, pe care D. Suciuc o analizează în directă legătură cu evoluția comunismului și revenind constant la paradigme explicative cu rădăcini în istoria Marilor Imperii din secolul al XIX-lea. Pentru istoricul clujean, realizarea proiectului Europei Unite, cu sprijin american, a reprezentat în primul rând o necesitate derivată din crearea blocului comunist, o formulă defensivă pe unul din fronturile Războiului Rece.

Nu avem de-a face, în lucrarea de față, cu o istorie a Uniunii Europene ci, după cum o spune și titlul, cu istoria evoluției unei idei, urmărită permanent prin prisma contextului care îi condiționează metamorfozele. Dincolo de viziunea foarte personală („*...ne-am propus să reconstituim, așa cum o intuim noi și în linii foarte generale, microsinteza rezultată din evoluția istoriei moderne și contemporane a Europei*”) (p. 5-6), trebuie remarcată scriitura extrem de aerisită, cartea constituinduse, dincolo de conținutul științific, într-o agreabilă lectură.

Vlad Popovici

Simion COSTEA, *Ideea Europeană și interesele statelor*, Cluj-Napoca, Edit. Napoca Star, 2005, 278 p.

Simion Costea is a lecturer in the university of Târgu-Mureș, where he teaches courses of European Integration History. He finished his university studies as best student in 1996. He is highly appreciated and recommended by many Historians with great value, like Vasile Vese, Adrian Ivan and Ioan Ciupercă, and many others who also referred his book favorably.

The book is focused mainly on the case of the Briand European unity project, which is in fact the Ph. D. work of the author, but from the general title it is not visible.

The introduction itself is not long, but very substantial, in which the Author illustrates his firm and complete theoretical knowledge in this field, and also specifies his work's its main objectives, its methodology, the used sources and the structure of the entire work.

The first chapter bears the title “The concept of Europe and European Integration. Political and Cultural Aspects” (Conceptul de Europa și integrarea europeană, aspecte politice și culturale). It contains mostly a theoretical approach, which tries to give a definition to the concept of Europe from a geographical, cultural and political point of view, presenting, explaining and analyzing the ideas of European unity which existed during history. But he is doing all these in a selective way, and without entering too much into details, till the beginning of the XXth century.

In the next chapter “The idea of Europe during the centuries and its reflections in school textbooks from interwar Romania” (Idea de Europa de-a lungul secolelor și reflectarea sa în

manualele de istorie universală) represents an original approach, characterized by interdisciplinary and courage, and it is meant to analyze and synthesize the approach of interwar Romanian historical education regarding to everything that can be called to be “European”. This chapter is very well structured, and could be published in almost any periodical with academic value (both in Romania and outside the country) as a separate study. It deals with History, Philosophy, Sociology and Educational Sciences in the same time, and uses both their methods and contents. The chapter probably was conceived to have not only a scientific, but also an educational “propagandistic” value too, while it tries to prove the existence of a connection between European unity ideas and the main representatives of Romanian cultural life from those years, analyzing textbooks written by Nicolae Iorga, Andrei Ōetea, Ioan Lupaş, P. P. Panaitescu etc.

Chapter no. 3, “The ideal of European Union and the different interests of states” (Idealul Uniunii Europene în confruntare cu interesele divergente ale statelor) analyses the relationship between interwar European states foreign policy and their ideas of European collaboration, cooperation and unity. The most cited sources are the Archives of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs from Bucharest, the Geneva fund. Obviously, the idea expressed by this title could be the subject of several dozens of Ph. D. thesis, and as a chapter, it represents only the introduction for the next one.

The fourth chapter is larger than the previous three all together, and bears the title „Reactions of Great Powers which decided the faith of Briand European Unity project” (ReacŃiile marilor puteri care au decis soarta proiectului Briand de Uniunea Europeană). In this chapter it is used especially the methodology characteristic for research in the field of International Relations studies. It summarizes, the attitude of diverse European Great Powers toward political realities existing at that time in Europe, and also their attitude toward the Briand project. The biggest space in the analyses is dedicated to Weimar Germany, the author having a very harsh critical position toward the attitude of this state. There are analyzed, in the same chapter, the points of view of Great Britain, Italy and the Soviet Union. Among the sources are books and Archive documents too.

The chapter “The position of the states from Central Europe toward the Briand European Unity project” (PoziŃiile statelor din Europa centrală faŃă de proiectul Briand de Uniune Europeană) is similar as subject and methods to the previous one. It presents a perspective in comparison, the attitude toward the Briand project of the following East- and central European states: Yugoslavia, Czechoslovakia, Poland, Hungary and Romania. Main sources are the diplomatic Archives from Geneva and France, and in the case of Romania – not in the other ones too – certain collection of documents from inside the country’s archives.

“The Committee for the Study of the European Unity project (1930-1937). Romania: founding and active member of the European Commission” (Comisia de studiu pentru Uniunea Europeană, 1930-1937. România: membru fondator Ńi activ al Comisiei Europene) represents the sixth chapter of the work and it is dedicated to the works of the European Committee which examined and debated the project itself. The main accent is put on the activity of Romanian diplomats and specialists, and this is done in an extremely detailed way, being analyzed the works of each session in part, with its events and consequences.

At the end, as a summary, there are presented the main events of the European construction process from the end of World War II, in a chronologic way.

All in all, we can say that the book is a good one, well-written, with an interesting subject, about which the Romanian public knew less till this moment. It is very important that it presents, in the majority of cases, the position of Romania, Romanian politicians and intellectuals to the current European affairs of the period in discussion, especially on those related to the construction process (or, in case we want to date its beginning from the appearance of the ECSC: pre-construction process) of the common European identity and structures. Maybe this is the main mistake of the book too: talking too much about the position and opinions of Romanian thinkers, without saying clearly that these, as representatives of a small nation and small country, could create a false image for “amateur” readers. For example, it would have been probably useful to introduce some pages about the role of Romania in those times in the European policy and interstate political life. But we must admit that the book has its value from the point of view of History and Political Science and it also has a certain kind of moral role by bringing another proof for the fact that Romania and the Romanian nation are parts of Europe and also deserves their places in it.

Artur Lakatos